

BADICS TAMÁS¹

Competition in the Hungarian Banking Market²

As a result of the increasing dominance of the financial sector over the real economy, the competition and concentration in the banking market receive more and more attention. Besides this, the changes in the competition in the banking sector affect the stability of the financial system, one of the major goals of monetary policy.

In this paper, we overview the evolution of the main indices of competition and concentration and try to explore the main characteristics of the Hungarian banking sector.

Up to the financial crisis in 2008 the competition in the banking system was an intensively researched area in the Hungarian literature of finance owing to the fact that competition, besides its competition policy importance, is closely connected with the effectiveness of monetary policy. After the financial crisis the emphasis shifted from the competition to the stability of the bank system. In the following, we will demonstrate that in some segments the Hungarian banking market exhibited a rather low level of competition in the pre-crisis period, which was supported by both indicators of profitability and model calculations based on measures of interest rate pass-through or more complex models of bank behaviour. As will be seen, the low level of competition, which particularly characterized household loans and deposits, can be traced back to structural reasons, to the low level of financial culture of households and, in part, to regulatory reasons. The new regulation, effective from 2010, might change the situation somewhat – especially in the market of housing loans – but this is impossible to judge yet from the data available.

Concentration in the Hungarian Banking Market

The concentration of the Hungarian banking market – measured by the HHI index for the total assets of banks and for most of the submarkets – has been decreasing gradually for the last two decades. At the beginning of the 90s the relatively early – compared to other post-socialist countries in the region – privatisation of the banking system resulted in a highly concentrated

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² The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under grant agreement n° 266800.

banking market. Owing to the comparatively easy entrance conditions, the number of banks increased – mainly in the form of subsidiary banks of foreign owned banks – so, despite of the bank fusions from the second half of the 90s, the concentration – as measured either by the Herfindahl index or by the C3 or C5 indicator – began to decrease. Now the concentration of the Hungarian bank sector – relative to similar-size European countries – is average. However, as Várhegyi (2010) and Öcsi—Somogyi—Várhegyi (2008) emphasize it, certain segments of the whole financial market have remained rather concentrated. For example, in the case of household deposits the index exceeded 2500 around the end of the 90s, and in 2006 it was still at around a relatively high level of 1500 and in the case of forint-based housing loans the concentration reached 3300 and hired purchase loans approached the value of 4000 in 2006. See the table 1.

	2004	2005	2006
HUF housing loan	3478	3451	3326
CHF housing loan	2083	1597	1508
HUF personal loan	3390	3482	2638
CHF personal loan	3947	2311	2744
HUF hired purchase loan	3798	3548	3787
CHF home equity loans	-	2023	1302

Source: MNB (2007)

As the privatisation of the centralised bank system has preserved the dominance of OTP Bank, it is worth investigating the C1 indicator of the various submarkets (see table 2).

	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006
total assets	36	35	39	36	35	34
household deposits	45	47	44	42	42	39
household loans	39	29	49	51	51	49
number of branches	47	45	45	39	35	33

Source: Öcsi—Somogyi—Várhegyi (2008)

As it can be seen, as far as household deposits and household loans are concerned, OTP's market share approached even 40% and 50% respectively in 2006. As the market share of the leading bank is also an important indicator of competition³, the fusions between 2005 and 2010, in some measure, increased the competition too by eroding the market leader's position. Nevertheless, as Öcsi—Somogyi—Várhegyi (2008) point out, because the state interest subsidy was linked to the issuing of mortgage bonds, the establishment of collateral banks somewhat halted the steady decrease of the HHI of household loans. As a result of the peculiar state interest subsidy system,

³ Molyneux (1999) regards the distance between the leader and the second bank more important than the degree of concentration of the whole market.

OTB bank, owing to its own mortgage bank (OTP JZB), succeeded in increasing its market share in the mortgage loan market and cancelling the advantageous effect of consolidation.

The birth of mortgage banks was rendered possible by the Mortgage Act of 1997/XXX., by which the Hungarian mortgage market became modelled on the German one (see: Király—Nagy 2008). The role of mortgage banks began to strengthen only from 2001 owing to the governmental decree on preferential housing loans published in 2001. Among the mortgage banks OTP's JZB and FHB earned prominent share in the market, with the third biggest mortgage bank's share being negligible. The growth of these mortgage banks essentially stopped in 2003. The reasons were the cutback in the state interest subsidies in 2003 and the sudden increase in domestic interest rates in the same year.⁴

Competition in the Hungarian Banking Market

The high level of concentration in the household-related markets (deposits, housing loans) itself, still does not necessarily mean lack of competition⁵. However, the high level of interest rate margin⁶ (see Table 3), and even more the above-EU-average profitability of Hungarian banks are (see: Öcsi—Somogyi—Várhegyi (2008)) already the distinguishing signs of low level competition.

	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	real margin (2005)
<i>Hungary</i>	4.3	4.0	4.3	4.1	3.7	3.6
Poland	3.4	3.1	3.2	3.1	3.1	3.0
Slovenia	3.7	3.2	2.8	2.5	-	2.4
Slovakia	2.7	2.9	2.9	2.2	2.2	2.1
Czech Republik	2.4	2.1	2.3	2.2	2.3	2.2
Austria	-	-	1.2	1.0	1.0	1.0

Source: Öcsi—Somogyi—Várhegyi (2008)

⁴ This latter reason was the result of the sharp rise in the country's risk premium. As Király-Nagy (2008) emphasize, the five-year point of the yield curve climbed from a moderate level of 6% to 10 %.

⁵ According to the conventional approach of the theory of competition, the so called *Structure—Conduct—Performance-hypothesis*, there is a close relationship between the grade of concentration and the oligopolistic income of banks or competition. (A relatively recent empirical study underpinning this hypothesis is Tregenna (2009).) Other studies do not reinforce that concentration necessarily results in monopolistic profit (see: Scholtens (2000) and Bikker—Haaf (2001)), and there are alternative theories (*effective market structure- and contestability hypotheses*) that permit competition in the case of concentrated market structures. Claessens—Laeven (2003), in their study based on *H*-statistics, found, that there is a positive correlation between concentration and the grade of competition, underpinning the statement that from the point of view of competition, contestability is a more important factor than the actual presence of foreign banks or bank concentration, suggesting that a more contestable bank system faces greater competition.

⁶ The reason for the high margins – as Móri—Nagy (2004) remarks – may be higher inflation, higher credit risk, the higher proportion of customer loans in the asset structure of the banks which also means an additional risk, and the lack of scale efficiency arising from the small size of the market, the latter being a common feature of the, relatively to EU average, underdeveloped banking system. However, Hungarian interest rate gaps are higher than those of other East European countries even in real terms, (see the table) therefore it cannot be explained either by the underdeveloped banking system or the relatively high inflation rate.

In the last decades several articles have been published which investigate the competitive behaviour of banks empirically in a non-structural approach. Some of these researches were based on the investigation of interest rate pass-through and some on the so-called ‘new empirical industrial organization’ approach, which usually uses various alternative versions of Panzar-Rosse and the Bresnahan models.

Some of the first related articles (see: Világi (1996), Árvai (1998), Horváth—Krekó—Naszódi (2004) investigated the interest rate pass-through from market rates and policy rates to various types of lending and deposit rates. Horváth—Krekó—Naszódi (2004) point out that, although the pass-through had improved between the mid-90s and the beginning of 2000s, the interest rate pass-through is not complete in the long run, and is rather sluggish in the short run, and deposit rates or lending rates for households react much less than lending rates for the corporate sector. Although these articles investigated the behaviour of banks from the point of view of the transmission mechanism of the monetary policy, they raise the question of competition, and suggest that compared to developed countries, the slow pass-through in Hungary, to some extent, may be attributed to the low level of competition.

Várhegyi (2003), Várhegyi (2004), Móré—Nagy (2004) and Öcsi—Somogyi—Várhegyi (2008) use various types of the Panzar-Rosse model. These results confirm that in some submarkets banks use a kind of oligopoly pricing which is in harmony with the above-mentioned features of the banking market. According to empirical estimations, based on H -statistics, in some markets, mainly in the market of current account loans, trade loans, personal loans and demand deposits, the grade of competition is extremely low.

The Panzar—Rosse model tries to measure competition by means of H -statistics which sum the elasticity of the bank’s earnings with respect to the various input prices, that is

$$H = \sum (\partial IR / \partial FP_i) (FP_i / IR)$$

where IR denotes the bank’s interest earnings and FP_i denotes the price of the i^{th} input factor. The H -statistics of a bank is a number not greater than 1 and shows the extent to which a change in input prices is reflected in bank revenues. Number 1 represents the perfect competition and a number around 0 means a collusive market structure or monopoly and the numbers between the two extreme values pertain to monopolistic competition. The main advantage of this approach is that instead of using aggregate data concerning the whole bank sector, it makes use of bank-level data taking the specialities of the particular bank’s products and cost structure into account.

One of the first studies including the H -statistics of Hungarian banks is Claessens—Laeven (2003) which was based on the observation of 4479 banks in 50 different countries. The following table shows some of their findings concerning the H -statistics of a number of countries referring to data registered between 1994 and 2001. According to the data, the H -statistics of the Hungarian banking system is 0.75 which suggests that monopolistic competition is the best description of the competition in the Hungarian banking sector with relatively strong competition.

Várhegyi (2003) applied the Bikker—Haaf (2001) specification of the Panzar—Rosse model to measure the Hungarian loan market which she regarded as homogenous. She used the annual data of 18 banks using a panel system containing altogether 140 observations. The share of the banks investigated in total was about 80% of the total market according to their balance-sheet total and none of the banks’ share left out of the sample reached 2%. She found that there was monopolistic competition in this special market between H values of 0.56-0.67 which fitted the average of the EU countries, and the competition in this market increased during the period of 1995-2002.

Várhegyi (2004) and Móré—Nagy (2004) use an extended form of the Panzar—Rosse model, the Bresnahan (1982) model to measure competition in the Hungarian banking market (see also:

Coccorese (2002)). The Bresnahan model is a type of the so-called *conjectural variational oligopoly model*, which can take the collusive behaviour of banks into account.

Móré—Nagy (2004) measured the competition in the loan market and the deposit market separately for the period between December 1996 and September 2003, by measuring the conjectural variation parameters λ of the banks. Although, the EU deposit market was near complete competition (see: Bikker 2003), as for the Hungarian banking market, they found that in the Bresnahan model the competition in the loan and the deposit markets was between perfect competition and the Cournot equilibrium, but the competition of the consumer credit market fell between the Cournot equilibrium and perfect collusion.

Molnár—Nagy—Horváth (2007) used the *discrete-choice framework* (for early applications to bank systems see: Dick (2002) and Nakane *at al.* (2006)) to analyze the degree of competition in the Hungarian household credit and deposit markets. They estimated how much the banks' mark-up in the case of Bertrand price competition and in the case of perfect collusion would be and compared them to the observed mark-ups for the period of January 2003—December 2005. In this framework, if the observed mark-up is located between the mark-ups of the Bertrand competition and the perfect collusion, the degree of competition may be regarded to be low. In contrast to this, if the observed price falls below the hypothetical Bertrand point, the degree of competition is high. They calculated the observed and implied mark-ups for each month of the sample period and found that the degree of competition was low in the markets of personal loans, purchase loans and demand deposits and only the market of the long-term deposits could be regarded to be competitive.

Non-price Competition

An important deficiency of the above-detailed model calculations is that they can measure only the price competition in the banking sector. However, as Várhegyi (2008) remarks (see also: Király-Nagy (2008)), there are other forms of competition, such as *cost-based* and *risk-based competitions*. At the end of the 90s, the competition in the corporate loan market – owing to the presence of foreign owned banks in this segment – was increasingly strengthening. In this situation the foreign owned banks turned to the household loan market which was stimulated by the government's subsidizing of housing loans, a practice that reached its climax in 2002, and they engaged in a strong cost-based competition by increasing their marketing expenditure, opening new offices, installing new ATMs, increasing their employees and expanding the range of banking products and services. Local banks didn't take part in this competition but they succeed in preserving their position in the household market owing to their branch network and by utilizing their acquaintance with local clients.

In 2003 the situation in the Hungarian loan market fundamentally changed as a consequence of the decrease in state interest subsidies and the increase in interest rates. In this situation banks tried to maintain their income by acquiring new clients. This goal – as price-competition was not the main characteristic of the bank sector – was achieved by taking on increasingly greater credit risk. Risk-based competition manifested in the increase in loan-to-value (LTV), the ratio of instalments to income and the duration of loans, in the relaxation of conditions in the loan approval process, in the preferential instalments at the beginning of the life of the loans and in the appearance and the spread of foreign currency loans.

Another characteristic of risk-based competition has been the propagation of loan marketing through agents. Because most of the agent employed by banks are independent of banks and market a number of bank products, the propagation of loan marketing through agents enhance competition. On the other hand, loans intermediated by agents are more risky. Therefore, the propagation of loan marketing through agents decreases the stability of the bank systems.

Non-structural reasons for lack of competition

A number of studies draw attention to the underdevelopment of the financial culture of Hungarian households. The level of financial culture does not only affect financial stability – through the households' propensity to bear risks –, it also has an effect on the level of competition in the banking market. One of the key elements of financial culture is how conscious households are in deciding on their savings. More specifically, there are two areas of interest here: (1) the extent to which households are familiar with the various saving alternatives to bank deposits, (2) how sensitive households are to the prices of financial services. It is well-known that Hungarian households, as compared to the developed countries, invest a relatively small part of their financial wealth in financial funds, securities and insurance reserves, which is commonly regarded as a sign of low level of financial culture, and an important symptom of a low level of substitution between bank deposits and funds, which decrease the competition in these markets.

MNB (2010) also remarks, that the lack of price competition in the household banking segment can be attributed, in part, to regulatory reasons. In Hungary, contrary to a number of other emerging countries – for example Lithuania, Poland and Latvia – the interest rates are not fixed or tied to reference interest rates, thus allowing banks to change interest rates unilaterally during the repayment term of a loan. MNB (2010) and MNB (2011) draw attention to the fact that, owing to the non-transparent pricing practice of banks, loans are incomparable, and loan refinancing becomes impossible, as households do not shoulder the high cost of loan refinancing in exchange for uncertain gains.

It also impedes loan refinancing and therefore weakens competition that – according to the rules – prepayment of mortgage loans is more expensive when the debtor finances the prepayment by means of another bank's loan. This regulation, as MNB (2011) emphasizes, weakens competition, as this excess cost is not justifiable by higher operational outlays and therefore makes the replacement of loans unnecessarily expensive. Similarly, the wide and also unilaterally modifiable foreign exchange margins do not only enhance non-transparency but also make replacement expensive, because – as debtors' loan accounts are managed in HUF – the debtor, when refinancing the foreign exchange loan by another foreign exchange loan, must pay the margin twice.

MNB (2010) and MNB (2011) also mention another competition limiting rule regarding the refinancing of CHF loans. According to a 2010 amendment of the 361/2009 government decree, the replacement of CHF loans is possible only under 45-percent LTV ratio limit, while the replacement of loans denominated in forint or euro is possible independently of their LTV ratio. This rule made the replacement of most of the CHF denominated loans impossible by another CHF loan, as, in 2010, 85 per cent of the existing loans denominated in CHF had a LTV of more than 45 percent.

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